

5Q17 frag. 2 (Exod 22:10-12?)

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In DJD 3, J.T. Milik grouped together six fragments as 5Q17, with the qualification that frags. 1-3 and frags. 4-6 might not have belonged to one and the same manuscript, while one or more of 5Q18 frags. 5-8 might have belonged to 5Q17. Milik himself associated the wording of three of the 5Q17 fragments with Pentateuchal texts: frag. 1 would recall phraseology from Numbers, the sequence of letters of frag. 5 corresponds with Deut 5:21 and Exod 20:17 (variant), and the words of frag. 4 might fit well with Deut 28:36-37, even though the reconstructed lines would not have unequal length. One might add that frag. 6 could fit Gen 39:30-32.

In fact, the most certain case of textual overlap with a scriptural text is frag. 2. The fragment has broken into several pieces, but one can read its text with Exod 22:10-12 as follows:

]°°[1
ידו במלאכת רעהו ו[לקח בע[ליו ולא ישלם ואם גנב יגנב	2
מעמו ישלם לבעליו [אם טרוף] יטרף יבאהו	3

The letters on the left part of the uncleaned fragment (PAM 41.035) are not very clear, and on the photograph of the cleaned fragment (PAM 42.317) the left piece has broken off and been joined incorrectly. However, the pieces can be restored to their place as in DJD 3, Plate XLII, and on the Gimp-ed fragment (below).

The sequence of the words in these two lines only fits in Exod 22:10-12. Of the other 5Q17 fragments only frag. 6 might also fit Exodus, namely 20:17 if one reads ואמתו שון[ר]. Yet, fragment 1, even though it has the phrases כל העדה and היירדן as in Numbers, does not fit any scriptural text. If these

fragments indeed come from one and the same manuscript, that manuscript would rather have been, for example, a reworked Pentateuch manuscript.

DJD 3 M. Baillet, J.T. Milik, et R. De Vaux, *Les 'petites grottes' de Qumrân*, Discoveries in the Judaean Desert of Jordan III (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1962)

PAM photographs taken as screenshots from www.deadseascrolls.org.il